

SELECTED OPTIONS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF A STEAM METHANE REFORMER

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Abstract

Industrial hydrogen production via Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) is characteristic by a two-step production mechanism: a high-temperature catalytic reforming of hydrocarbons is followed by water gas shift reaction performed at lower temperatures. SMR units may employ one or two shift reactors. In this study we examined the possible means of increasing the efficiency and lowering the energy intensity of an industrial SMR unit: Addition of the low-temperature shift reactor and CO₂ removal from syngas via pressure swing adsorption. Both options were assessed by their impact on auxiliary fuel consumption, electricity consumption and maximal production capacity of the plant. The impact of changed high pressure steam export was included as well. Shift reactor addition reduced specific feed (natural gas) consumption but led to increased specific auxiliary fuel consumption with the overall change in the natural gas balance being close to zero. Carbon dioxide removal, even without its sequestration, reduced the energy intensity of the plant.

Introduction

The aim of this work is to analyze the impact of addition of low temperature shift (LTS) reactor and utilization of hydrogen separation process tailgas by reduction of CO₂ content. To fulfil the aims of proper evaluation of proposed alternatives, mathematical model of industrial hydrogen plant was constructed in Aspen Hysys V11 software. Scheme of this plant is visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of modelled hydrogen plant.

Natural gas entering the hydrogen plant is blended with small amount of recycled hydrogen for desulphurization of natural gas. After the compression and desulphurization, high pressure steam is added in projected ratio and this reaction mixture enters the reforming reactor, where steam reforming reactions take place. The amount of carbon monoxide present in the syngas produced in reforming reactor is greatly reduced at high temperature shift (HTS) reactor by water gas shift reaction. After the HTS reactor, reaction mixture is cooled down and hydrogen is separated at pressure swing adsorption (PSA) unit. Offgas from the PSA unit is combusted at the furnace of reforming reactor with enough natural gas to deliver the heat necessary for the endothermic steam reforming reactions. Flue gas, still at the high temperature, is then cooled down at convective section of reforming reactor furnace, while the steam is produced, and reaction mixture is preheated.

Modelling of hydrogen plant

The aim of modelling of hydrogen plant was to develop mathematical model able to evaluate the impact of proposed alternatives addition to the hydrogen plant. Model was based on the available documentation of an existing hydrogen plant. Scheme of developed model can be found in Figure 2. To avoid unnecessary robustness of model, several assumptions were considered, mainly quantitative reaction of all hydrocarbons higher than methane (C2+) and perfect combustion at the furnace of reforming reactor. Due to low content of odorization substances in natural gas and low impact on the plant energy balance, this process was neglected in terms of reactor simulation and instead was simulated by addition of heat exchanger, with the same temperature (15 °C) and pressure loss (50 kPa), as was projected for this process. Fluid package was chosen in accordance with the literature¹. Peng-Robinson fluid package was used, confirming the results obtained at the previous study².

Figure 2. Scheme of developed mathematical model in Aspen Hysys.

To simulate reforming reactor, equilibrium model was used with ATE, Approach to equilibrium, parameter. Usage of ATE parameter allows taking into account basically all of the effects on final composition of reaction mixture and sufficient compliance with operational data was obtained in MATLAB software². HTS (high temperature shift), was modelled in the same manner as reforming reactor – with the use of equilibrium model, at design pressure and inlet temperature, while equilibrium composition at the outlet of reactor was modified by ATE parameter. Comparison of design and modelled data is provided in Table I.

Water steam is produced in 3 steam generators, CONV_C, SGREF and SGHTS from 151°C feed water, preheated before entrance to steam generators in FWH heat exchanger. Calculations were made with the assumption of constant value of UA parameter [kW/K].

Table I
Comparison of design and calculated data

Mole %	Reforming reactor outlet		HTS reactor outlet	
	Design data	Aspen data	Design data	Aspen data
H ₂	71.57	71.51	73.93	73.95
CO	12.39	12.79	3.05	3.13
CO ₂	8.54	8.22	16.14	16.09
N ₂	0.23	0.23	0.21	0.21
CH ₄	7.27	7.24	6.67	6.62

Equipment addition

Consequently, the model was developed with proposed equipment for the analysis of LTS reactor addition and CO₂ content reduction at the PSA tailgas. Two equipment items were proposed, PSA unit for CO₂ separation and LTS reactor.

A. PSA unit for CO₂ separation from the reaction mixture (PSA-CO₂). Assumption for this PSA unit was the capture of solely carbon dioxide, which is the process first described in 1951³ unlike PSA unit for hydrogen separation (PSA-H₂), where every gas except hydrogen is captured. This way is change of hydrogen gas pressure reduced to unit pressure loss and there is no need to desorb the gas off the adsorbent. Efficiency of carbon dioxide separation was, in accordance with PSA-H₂ efficiency, assumed as 85.6%, with 99.9% purity of separated carbon dioxide – high purity was assumed to be reached by consequent liquefaction of captured carbon dioxide. Important for this alternative is the positioning of PSA-CO₂ unit in the hydrogen plant⁴. As the most favourable, position immediately before the PSA-H₂ unit was chosen. Main advantage of this position is avoidance of need for the compressor. Another big advantage is lowering of carbon dioxide content of gas entering the PSA-H₂ unit. This results in the increase of PSA-H₂-offgas heating value, which can possibly reduce consumption of natural gas in the reforming reactor furnace and further reduce carbon emissions. Scheme of this equipment is in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Scheme of PSA-CO₂ unit addition to the plant.

B. To support the conversion of carbon monoxide, which is produced in reforming reactor by reaction (2), addition of low temperature shift reactor was considered. Like the HTS reactor, this reactor was also modelled as equilibrium reactor, while ATE parameter value was assumed to be the same as in HTS reactor. LTS reactor size was chosen to be equal to HTS reactor size⁵ and temperature at the inlet of this reactor was 200°C, to minimise the risk of thermal degradation of catalyst at temperature higher than 260°C⁶. Proposed position of this reactor in the scheme is after the FWH heat exchanger, as can be seen in Figure 3. To achieve desired temperature of LTS reactor inlet, operating conditions of FWH heat exchanger were changed, so the temperature of reaction mixture at the outlet of FWH remains at 200 °C. To utilize heat of reaction mixture at the outlet of LTS reactor, another heat exchanger, FWPH was proposed, to preheat feed water before entering FWH heat exchanger. Reaction mixture in this proposed heat exchanger is cooled down to 168 °C, to avoid condensation of unreacted water steam. Scheme of this proposed equipment is visualised in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Scheme of LTS reactor addition to the plant.

Methodology

Four production rates of hydrogen were simulated: 3.4 t/h, that is maximum production capacity of modelled industrial plant, 3.0 t/h, 2.7 t/h and 2.4 t/h, which are standard production rates throughout the year. Each of proposed alternatives was used, while the process-side pressure loss during maximum capacity was calculated. Results of simulations were compared with the reference H₂ plant with the emphasis on CO₂ emissions and energy consumption. Economic evaluation was calculated for annual average hydrogen production of 2.7 t/h. Natural gas energy savings (NGES) were calculated by equation (1), from the difference in reference natural gas consumption (NG_{ref}) and actual natural gas consumption (NG_{mod}). To obtain results in kJ/h, high heat value (q_{NG}) was added to equation. Compensation mechanism of refinery steam network was also taken into account, so the reduction of steam production resulted in rise of fuel consumption at refinery power plant. Thus, steam energy savings (SES), equation (2), were calculated from the difference in reference (SP_{ref}) and actual (SP_{mod}) production of steam, which was multiplied by steam condensing heat value (h_s) and divided by refinery power plant efficiency (η_{PP}).

$$NGES = (NG_{ref} - NG_{mod})q_{NG} \quad (4)$$

$$SES = \frac{(SP_{ref} - SP_{mod})h_s}{\eta_{PP}} \quad (5)$$

Every change of steam production in hydrogen plant is manifested in power plant fuel consumption, which is also linked with the change of total carbon emissions of refinery – this was included in equation (3) for calculation of carbon dioxide emissions savings.

$$CES = (CE_{ref} - CE_{mod}) + \frac{(SP_{ref} - SP_{mod})h_s}{q_{PP}\eta_{PP}} EF_{PP} \quad (6)$$

Electricity consumption of liquefaction process was assumed to be 98 kWh/t of CO₂⁷. Capital costs needed for the liquefaction unit was taken from the same source, as 67.15 mil. USD for the liquefaction of 316 t/h of carbon dioxide, in 2012. Emissions from the electricity grid were not taken into account. All of equipment prices were adapted to current prices using CECPI parameter and indirect costs of 160% of equipment price were assumed when calculating total capital costs.

Results

Table II provides an overview of proposed alternatives, pressure loss at maximum capacity of hydrogen plant and total capital cost, as well as operating costs. Each alternative was able to fulfil pressure limits of refinery hydrogen network of 2.0 MPa.

Table II
Overview of proposed alternatives for hydrogen plant modification

Alternative	Equipment addition	Pressure. loss / H ₂ press. [kPa]	Total capital cost [thousand €]	Operating costs [thousand €]
PSA	PSA-CO ₂ unit	150 / 2150	8 680	41.8
PSA+LTS	PSA-CO ₂ unit + LTS reactor	280 / 2100	9 280	81.7
LTS	LTS reactor	130 / 2250	588	39.9

Savings in comparison with reference hydrogen plant can be observed in Figure 5. These savings already take into account reduction of steam production and simultaneous increase of fuel consumption in refinery power plant. These savings represent 2-3% of total energy consumption of H₂ production process, including natural gas consumption as feed in the H₂ production.

This decrease is enabled by higher heating value of PSA tailgas from the hydrogen separation – as the amount of CO₂ present in the tailgas is significantly reduced, fuel consumed for heating this part of the tailgas is no longer needed, which results in lower consumption of natural gas as the fuel of reforming reactor furnace. Despite the reduction of steam production, which was considered to be compensated by refinery power plant with the energy efficiency of 85%, total natural gas consumption is decreased.

Alternative PSA+LTS results in similar results. However, as more hydrogen can be produced from the natural gas used as the process feed, energy savings are higher in comparison with PSA alternative. Still, lower carbon

monoxide content in PSA-H2 offgas slightly increases consumption of natural gas in the furnace, to the point it outweighs reduction of natural gas consumption as the feed in the process. However, higher consumption of natural gas in the furnace could be balanced out by rise in the steam production, which can reduce fuel consumption in refinery power plant. This effect can be observed in the LTS alternative – despite the decrease of natural gas consumption as the process feed, no significant change of total energy consumption is visible, due to higher fuel consumption. The decrease of power plant fuel consumption is not able to compensate for higher fuel consumption in the furnace of reforming reactor.

Figure 5. Energy savings of proposed alternatives in comparison with reference plant

As the decrease of natural gas consumption is also connected to the decrease of the carbon dioxide emissions, naturally, the next step is to analyze the impact of proposed alternatives on savings of carbon dioxide emissions. Due to the rise of carbon emission allowances price, decrease of carbon dioxide emissions significantly contributes to the total economic impact. Savings of carbon dioxide emissions can be observed in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Carbon dioxide savings of proposed alternatives in comparison with reference plant.

As results in Figure 6 suggests, PSA and PSA+LTS alternatives bring in significant decrease of carbon dioxide emissions, which are not outweighed by carbon dioxide emitted from the fuel combusted in central power plant. In accordance with the results observable in Figure 5, addition of sole LTS reactor does not bring in sufficient savings of natural gas and neither carbon dioxide emissions. However, it should be mentioned that the savings in PSA and PSA+LTS alternative are achieved by capturing and liquefaction of carbon dioxide. Because of this, subsequent economic evaluation is necessary.

Considering long-term course of futures contract for natural gas and electricity on Prague Stock Exchange⁸, assumption was made, that electricity price can be considered as 2.5 times higher than that of natural gas. Then payback period was calculated, results can be seen in Table III. Using the assumption of price relation of natural gas and electricity, low sensitivity of payback period on changes in prices of natural gas means, that energy savings obtained by CO₂ elimination from the tailgas covers most of costs for CO₂ liquefaction.

Table III
Overview of payback periods (in years) for various prices of natural gas and carbon dioxide emissions allowances

CO ₂ allowances price [€/t]	30				60	80
NG price [€/MWh]	20	50	80	110	80	80
PSA	2.68	2.57	2.47	2.38	1.30	0.99
PSA+LTS	2.49	2.37	2.27	2.17	1.20	0.92
LTS	16.47	12.13	9.61	7.95	6.65	5.52

Conclusion

As energy savings achieved by PSA-CO₂ addition are able to cover expenses for CO₂ liquefaction, with the current prices of emission allowances, short payback period is good promise for the next scientific works. Addition of LTS reactor alone has quite long age of return and reduction of CO₂ emission is almost negligible. However, PSA-CO₂ unit fairly enhances achieved savings, if used in the combination. Next work should be aimed at the development of rigorous mathematical model, mainly to include dependence of heat transfer coefficients on the flowrates, which could provide us with more detailed results on the decrease of steam production. Also, more detailed research of current advances in carbon dioxide separation by adsorption should be performed, to evaluate accepted assumptions for PSA-CO₂, like 87 % recovery of CO₂ and purity above 99.9%.

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